

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN ATHLETES IN THE SPORT OF BASKETBALL

Mavlanov Donyor Ergash ogli

Alfraganus university,

Teacher of the Department of Psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18428392>

Abstract: This thesis provides information on the social and psychological analysis of interpersonal relationships between basketball athletes.

Keywords: interpersonal relationships, group, communication, large group, small group, sociometry.

Introduction. The individual development of a person in a social environment takes place in the process of conscious and unconscious relationships and social communication. Interpersonal relationships of students in various educational institutions (school, AL, KKK, OO'YU) are a social and psychological phenomenon that occurs as a result of interaction in the process of communication. In this regard, first of all, it is necessary to dwell on the concept of relationships and communication.

Research objective. Communication and interpersonal relationships are the subject of social psychology. Communication is a leading activity performed by people, satisfying the most important human need - the need to live in society and to be connected with oneself as a person.

Methods of organizing research. Interpersonal relationships are subjectively experienced relationships between people, which are objectively manifested in the ways of influencing each other, in the nature of relationships in the process of joint activity and communication. A person's interaction with other people is of decisive importance in his attitude to activity - increased activity, tension, resourcefulness, or, conversely, heaviness, lack of initiative.

Y.L.Kolominsky investigated the system of interpersonal relationships in a student community mainly by the method of sociolatory in various environmental conditions (in the classroom, outside the classroom, in extracurricular activities). In interpersonal relationships, each person performs one or more roles. At first glance, this is quite difficult to determine, only with the help of special tests conducted in the community can one identify the "rejected", "isolated" people in the group.

According to the results of the study conducted by F.S.Ismagilova, in order for the interaction and communication that occurs in the student and student team not to take a negative turn, it is possible to teach the team members to solve

any problems together by constantly holding educational and business games and debates in groups.

In sports teams, the development of positive relationships in the physical and mental preparation of athletes for training and competitions is the main factor of victory. In a basketball team, it is easy to achieve the main goal - victory - only if the goal of each player is derived from the general goal of the team, and the team athletes are proud of being members of this team. Basketball players united in the spirit of strong faith in victory attract many new athletes to their team. However, unpleasant events that arise as a result of the breakdown of positive relationships between team athletes create various negative psychological states in athletes. In particular, team members develop negative relationships such as distrust of each other, dissatisfaction with each other's performance, injustice, and disorder. If the coach or team psychologist does not eliminate the negative emotions that hinder team members with great knowledge and skill, the team's athletes will suffer successive defeats, and the quality of the game will decrease. As a result, athletes are forced to move to other teams due to the unhealthy spiritual and moral relations in the team. Such negative aspects of the athletes' behavior may also have been formed in sports clubs or sports teams.

Therefore, we should not provide athletes with only one-sided education in sports teams (which applies to all team sports). Some coaches will pay less attention to an athlete who has suffered a series of consecutive defeats in competitions. As a result, the athlete will distrust the coach, team, and peers. As a result of this distrust, the athlete feels humiliated and negative qualities begin to develop in him. Therefore, the coach must treat each student as an individual. If the coach does not help to correct the shortcomings of the athletes, does not treat them as his own children, does not know how to help them get out of difficult situations, unpleasant situations will arise in the team, and the team will not be able to fulfill the task set for itself. Such coaches cannot be real educators.

A team, an athlete's team, sports classes, a sports training group, children's and youth sports schools are small groups. Athletes in a small group often communicate face to face. Developing positive relationships in the physical and mental preparation of athletes for training and competitions in groups plays an important role in improving their spiritual and moral qualities. Positive relationships help to eliminate unpleasant situations, sadness and other emotional experiences that arise in groups in various situations. It has been scientifically proven that the use of the methods of "Sociometry" and K.Thomas's "Cooperation" gives good results in studying relationships in sports teams.

Research results and discussion. For every practitioner, psychologist, teacher and coach working in the field of sports, the use of the sociometric method is very useful in scientific research, in the process of sports training and competitions, in team management, in transforming athletes into a strong team, in studying the socio-psychological state of athletes in groups. Sociometry is a kind of criterion, measurement, which mainly consists of questions. The main task of this method is to determine the characteristics of the relationships between team members.

In conclusion, we can say that the activities of sports teams consist of the interaction of individuals in solving certain problems together, and its most important condition is interpersonal relationships. Along with technical and tactical preparation for team results, interpersonal relationships in the group also play a large role, and ensuring a healthy social environment in the team, taking into account the individuality of athletes, can lead to an increase in the effectiveness of sports results.

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